

Herbal oral spray for sore throat: A review

Neha-Sanjay-Randhe, Kartika-Dhanraj-Rathi, Pallavi-Sunil-Rathod and Archana-Kajale-Kulkarni *

Department of Pharmaceutics, Yavatmal Zilla Vikas Samiti's Pataldhamal Wadhwani College of Pharmacy, Yavatmal. Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University.

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Abstract

Sore throat is a common condition of the oral cavity associated with pain, burning sensation, difficulty in swallowing, swelling, irritation or discomfort. Meanwhile sore throat is also known as pharyngitis. Sore Throat is caused by staphylococcus aureus, Escherichia coli, streptococcus pyrogen and other pathogenic bacteria while other non-infectious cause of sore throat includes environment allergens, dry air, smoking, pollution. Conventional treatment such as paracetamol, ibuprofen, and antibiotics like penicillin v, amoxicillin, etc are used, but they often provide only temporary relief and may cause adverse effects like burning, nausea, vomiting, itching etc. Herbal Oral spray offers a promising alternative due to their advantages, including rapid absorption, bypassing hepatic first pass metabolism, improved patient compliance, painless administration, and suitability for both local and systemic delivery. Herbal drugs such as Tulsi, Ginger, Mint, Clove, Aloe vera and Honey etc. possess multiple therapeutic activities including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, analgesic and wound-healing properties, making them potential candidates for sore throat management. The oral herbal throat spray has faster absorption as compared to swallowing pills or capsules and hence it is cost effective. Bioavailability of the herbal oral spray is high. These formulations are prepared using diverse techniques including maceration, sterilization, etc.

Keywords: Herbal Throat Sprays; Sore Throat Treatment; Oral Spray Formulation; Plant-Based Medicine; Phytochemicals; Drug Delivery Systems

1. Introduction

1.1. Definition

Sore throat is an acute upper respiratory tract infection that affects the respiratory mucosa of the throat. Since infections can affect any part of the mucosa, it is often arbitrary whether an acute upper respiratory tract infection is called "sore throat" ("pharyngitis" or "tonsillitis"), "common cold", "sinusitis", "otitis media", or "born chitis. Sometimes, all areas are affected (simultaneously or at different times) in one illness. In this chapter, we aim to cover people whose principal presenting symptom is sore throat. This may be associated with headache, fever, and general malaise. Suppurative complications include acute otitis media (most commonly), acute sinusitis, and peritonsillar abscess (quinsy). Non-suppurative complications include acute rheumatic fever and acute glomerulonephritis.[1]

Mouth ulcers, also known as aphthous ulcers, are common oral lesions that cause discomfort and pain, often interfering with daily activities such as eating and speaking. These ulcers can be classified into minor, major, and herpetiform ulcers, with varying degrees of severity and duration. The etiology of mouth ulcers is multifactorial, with potential causes including trauma, nutritional deficiencies (such as deficiencies in vitamin B2, B9, and B12), stress, infections, and autoimmune conditions. Current treatments primarily focus on symptom management, utilizing topical analgesics, antiseptics, anti-inflammatory agents, and corticosteroids to alleviate pain and accelerate healing.

* Corresponding author: Archana S. Kulkarni

Mouth ulcer sprays have emerged as a promising alternative to conventional topical treatments such as gels and ointments. These sprays offer several advantages, including ease of application, rapid absorption, and targeted delivery of active ingredients to the affected area.[2]

Mouth ulcer also known as cankers ulcer are normally small painful abscess that can develop in your mouth or the base of your gum due to these, we feel uncomfortable in eating, drinking and talking. Women's, adolescent and people with a family history of mouth ulcers are higher risk for developing mouth ulcer. There is no major drug therapy required for treatment of mouth ulcer, usually people prefer home remedies. But it is not convenient to take, dose variation may occur because there is no definite quantity given, and also it is unpleasant sometimes irritable thus accordingly we formulate candy like formulation that is lozenges which composed of herbal ingredient like, guava leaves, pigeon pea leave, Tulsi, mint, turmeric, liquorice, clove bended with dextrose, which is convenient for patient[3]

Figure 1 (A) Mechanisms through which topically applied beneficial lactobacilli can act against respiratory viral disease, and (B) Rationale for selection of Lactobacillus strains for topical application against respiratory viral disease. The modes of action experimentally explored in this study are indicated in bold frames. AECs, airway epithelial cells; APC, antigen- presenting cell; IFN, interferon; Teff, T effector cell (based on Spa Cova et al., 2021). [4]

1.2. Symptoms [5]

- Painful sore or lesion in the mouth.
- Burning sensation.
- Difficulty in eating, drinking or speaking.
- Swelling or redness in the affected area.
- Fever, swollen lymph nodes.

Figure 2 Oral cavity [6]

1.3. Advantages of oral spray over the other dosage form drug delivery systems [7]:

- The oral method of delivery is also very helpful for individuals who have trouble swallowing pills or capsules and it is cost effective because a smaller dosage is required.
- It's possible that faster absorption will result in a rapid commencement of effect.
- Patient compliance for disabled bedridden patients, as well as for travellers and busy people without ready access to water.
- Direct access to the systemic circulation through the internal jugular vein bypasses drugs from the hepatic first pass metabolism leading to high bioavailability.
- Low enzymatic activity.
- Suitability for drugs or excipients that mildly and reversibly damages or irritates the mucosa.
- Painless administration.
- Easy drug withdrawal.
- Facility to include permeation enhancer/enzyme inhibitor or pH modifier in the formulation.
- Versatility in designing as multidirectional or unidirectional release systems for local or systemic actions etc.

1.4. Disadvantages of Oral Sore Throat:

- Pain and Discomfort - Sore throat causes significant pain, especially when swallowing, speaking, or eating, leading to a decrease in daily functioning.[8]
- Difficulty in Eating and Drinking- sore throat often reduces appetite and fluid intake, increasing the risk of dehydration and malnutrition, especially in children and the elderly.[9]
- Disturbed Sleep and Daily Activities- Constant irritation and pain can disrupt sleep and affect productivity, leading to fatigue and reduced quality of life.[10]
- Risk of Complications- If left untreated, oral sore throat (especially from bacterial causes) may lead to tonsillitis, ear infections, or sinusitis.[11]
- Recurrent or Chronic Conditions- Chronic sore throat may indicate underlying problems like acid reflux, allergies, or postnasal drip.[12]

2. Possible Herbal drug candidate for formulation of Oral sore throat

2.1. Tulsi extract

Tulsi powder is procured from the local market, and its extract is made using ethanol. Holy basil, or Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum* L.), is a traditional Ayurvedic remedy that may help relieve sore throats. Fresh and dried leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn., a member of the Lemnaceae family, are used to make Tulsi extract. It has several phenolic compounds (antioxidants) and significant amounts of eugenol, which has been studied for its potential therapeutic effects in various microbial infections, including sore throat and pharyngitis. Eugenol makes up roughly 71% of the volatile oil in 0.7% of *Ocimum sanctum* leaves, whereas methyl eugenol makes up 20%. The volatile oil of Tulsi leaves contains eugenol,

carvacrol, linalool and methyl carvacrol. It has been demonstrated that these active components are primarily responsible for medicinal potential of the Tulsi plant to treat sore throats. It has several different bioactivities, including anticancer, antispasmodic, antifertility, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antifungal, analgesic, antidiabetic. Gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria are both equally effectively combated by Tulsi leaf extract. It provides protection against nearly every kind of illness brought on by bacteria, fungus, viruses, and protozoa.[13]

2.2. Ginger Extract

Ginger powder is procured from the local market, and its extract has been prepared from ginger powder by using ethanol as solvent and maceration as the process of extraction. Ginger is the root of the perennial plant *Zingiber officinale* belonging to the Zingiberaceae family. Gingerols, gingerenone A, zingerone, shogaols, paradols, quercetin, 6 dehydrogingerdione and other beneficial phenolic compounds are found in ginger. Ginger is a potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant due to all these active ingredients. Ginger is said to provide numerous health benefits, including a reduction in pain, swelling and inflammation. Analgesic and strong anti-inflammatory properties were reported for 6 gingerol, a dried ginger extract, and an extract enhanced with dried ginger. In comparison to antibiotics, ginger was discovered to have a stronger antibacterial impact against *Streptococcus pyrogens* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. When it comes to throat infections, ginger has an anti-inflammatory property thus making it one of the active ingredients to be used in throat spray.[14]

2.3. Mint extract

Mint powder is procured from fresh mint leaves obtained from local market. It is dried, powdered and its ethanolic extract has been prepared. Mint or more precisely the genus *Mentha*, is a group of perennial herbaceous plants that belong to the Lemnaceae family. The most popular species are *Mentha piperita*, which is peppermint, and *Mentha spicata*, which is spearmint. It is usually referred as pudina. Because of its cooling and anti-inflammatory qualities, mint leaves-especially peppermint (*Mentha piperita*)-have long been used to relieve sore throat. One of peppermint's key phytoconstituents, menthol, gives a cool feeling and aids in reducing throat inflammation, which relieves irritation. *Mentha* shows antibacterial properties against *Pseudomonas aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aerogenous* and *Streptococcus aureus*. The anti-inflammatory qualities of mint aid in reducing throat inflammation and swelling, which eases pain and discomfort.[15]

2.4. Clove extract

Cloves vary in length from about 1/2 to 3/4 inch and contain 14-20% essential oil. Cloves are strongly pungent due to their high content of eugenol, which can be extracted by distillation to yield the essential oil. Clove buds have been regarded as safe when taken orally for medicinal use. Cloves have been used by humans for medicinal applications for over two thousand years cloves also grow naturally in India, the West Indies, Tanzania, Sri Lanka, Brazil and Madagascar. With their sultry sweet aromatic flavour and powerful essential oil compounds, cloves have been used for hundreds of years as a nutritional spice for food and a remedy for a variety of health concerns. It is an ever-green plant of 10 to 20 m in height with spear-shaped leaves and racemiferous yellowish flowers, has a strong phenolic smell and sharp acrid taste, whereas, essential oil of clove is a colourless or light yellowish fluid extracted from dried flower buds of *Eugenia* has properties like anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antipyretic, antifungal and used in ulcer treatment, anti-inflammatory activity.[16]

2.5. Honey extract

Medicinal importance of honey is known since ancient times. It is said to possess antimicrobial property as well as wound healing activity. Honey though mainly made up of sugars and water also contains vitamin B complex and C with lots of minerals such as calcium, potassium, and zinc. Its broad-spectrum antibacterial property against pathogenic bacteria and oral bacteria like *staphylococcus* and *pseudomonas* has been proved. Honey is known for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties in literature. Sore throat is one of the common symptoms of patients visiting our ear, nose and throat (ENT) outpatient department (OPD). It can be because of various inflammatory and infective causes such as allergies, reflux disease, sinus drainage, and tonsillitis. Sore throat can be of viral or infective etiology. Various treatments tried for sore throat have not given satisfactory results. In various studies, residents have been found to use honey for pharyngitis and respiratory ailments. However, no scientific data are available in literature regarding the same. Hence, we plan to conduct this study to find out if honey has some role as an antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant in treatment of sore throat [17].

3. Synthetic drug uses for sore throat:

- Paracetamol
 - Ibuprofen
 - Antibiotics: e.g. Penicillin v, Amoxicillin, Azithromycin, cefuroxime, Augmentin (Amoxicillin & clavulanic acid) [18]
 - Synthetic oral spray formulations are available in market:
 - Nitro-glycerine (NTG) oral spray.
 - Delta 9-tetrahydrocannabinol/cannabidiol Oro muscular spray.
 - Aqwet oral spray.
 - Carboxin oral spray.
 - Flurbiprofen throat spray.
 - Herbal throat spray are available:
 - Glyceryl trinitrate spray.
 - Zolpimist oral spray.
 - Biotoque botanical's clove spray [19].
-

4. Possible method of preparation of oral herbal spray for sore throat

4.1. Method 1:

Take a 25 ml Distilled water boil it

↓

Then add clove oil, oregano oil, peppermint oil, rose oil, mannitol

↓

Mix well and boil for 15 min.

↓

Cool it and filter it.

↓

Filled in suitable container.[20]

4.2. Method 2 :

Take a beaker

↓

add all oils in it with continuous stirring.

↓

After mixing, boil the mixture in water bath for 10-15 minutes.

↓

Cool the mixture at room temperature and filter it through the filter paper.

↓

Filled the mixture in a suitable container [21]

4.3. Method 3

Sodium benzoate, potassium sorbate, sucralose, and grapefruit powder flavour were dissolved in the required amount of purified water using a magnetic stirrer.

↓

A mucoadhesive polymer was added

↓

mixed, and left until complete swelling

↓

the formation of a low-viscosity homogeneous solution had taken place

↓

In a separate container, essential oils of lavender and grapefruit were dissolved in ethyl alcohol 96%; clove CO₂ extract was added

↓

mixed with the necessary amount of water,

↓

The resulting API emulsion was added into a solution with mucoadhesive and mixed

↓

after 3–5 min until a homogeneous system was formed.[22]

4.4. Method 4

Frozen crude propolis was first grounded using a grinder.

↓

then extracted with 70% ethanol and stirred for 24 h at room temperature.

↓

the extract was kept at –18 °C for another 24 h and finally filtered to remove wax.

↓

For oral/throat spray formulation, the obtained propolis extract was ground with liquid nitrogen.

↓

fine particles dissolved in food-grade alcohol in an ultrasound water bath.

↓

MCT was added to propolis solution in alcohol and vortexed for 2 min.

↓

After that, α -tocopherol was dissolved in cold-pressed black cumin oil.

Finally, cold-pressed black cumin oil together with α -tocopherol and all essential oils were combined with the alcoholic mixture of propolis and MCT by vortexing for 5 min. develop the current formulation [23].

5. Evaluation parameter for oral spray

5.1. Appearance

The appearance of the spray solution is evaluated visually, for clarity and colour.

5.2. pH

The pH of the optimized spray solution is calculated using the digital pH meter. The pH meter is adjusted using a phosphate buffer of different pH values (4.0 and 7.0) before calculating the pH of the optimized formulation. Finally, the pH was determined for the spray solution.

5.3. Evaporation Time

Evaporation time is needed to dry the spray. It is measured by spraying the formulation on a glass slide and the drying time is noted using a stop clock.

5.4. Spray pattern

The formulation is sprayed on pH-sensitive paper. The distance separating the container from the target was kept constant at 5cm. Then, the spray pattern is evaluated by spraying the concentrate in vertical and horizontal positions. Finally, the sprayed diameter is noted. The maximum diameter (D_{max}) and minimum diameter (D_{min}) was noted. The diameter ratio is calculated by ratio D_{max} and D_{min} . Diameter ratio= D_{max} / D_{min} Where D_{min} and D_{max} are the maximum and minimum diameters of the spray pattern respectively.

5.5. Spray Angle

The two parameters are correlated with the polymer concentration and viscosity of the formulation. The spray angle should be less than 85° for easy actuation of drug solution from the container and to cover the maximum surface area. The sprays are actuated horizontally onto a white paper mounted 10 cm from the nozzle. Spray angle (θ) = $\tan^{-1} (l/r)$.

5.6. The Volume of each Spray

The volume of each spray is calculated using the equation given below. An average of five sprays is calculated.

$$(V_s) = (W_t - W_o)/D$$

Where V_s is the volume of sprayed; W_t is the weight of solution after spray; W_o is the initial weight of solution in the container; D is density.

5.7. Viscosity

The viscosity of the solution is determined by the Oswald viscometer. 20ml solution is filled in Oswald viscometer. The flow of solution is measured in time from A to B point in the viscometer. Reading is taken at least three times. The viscosity of the spray solution is measured against the viscosity of water. The viscosity of the solution is evaluated visually and rated as low (water-like), medium (glycerol-like), or high (syrup-like).

5.8. Droplet Size

Microscopic method is generally employed for the measurement of particle size the in range of 0.2 to $100\mu\text{m}$. The formulation is sprayed on a clean glass slide and at least sizes of 10 particles are measured under a microscope. The droplet size is calculated using micrometres under low magnification. The droplet size is characterized once the spray was fully developed. Fine particles should be as low as possible to avoid droplet deposition in the lower airways.

5.9. Drug Content

Formulation is determined by mixing formulation with appropriate solvent for complete drug extraction. The solution then filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter and subjected to colorimetric analysis. Drug content is calculated from a linear regression equation using the standard curve. Sample from the drug-free spray will use as a blank solution during analysis.[24]

6. Components of oral throat spray

6.1. Grooved Button

- Positioned at the top of the actuator.
- Helps the patient correctly orient the spray, even in the dark.
- Ensures the nozzle is directed toward the buccal cavity for accurate dosing.

6.2. Nozzle

- The outlet through which the drug formulation is expelled as a fine mist.
- Designed to produce uniform spray droplets, improving absorption across the mucosal surface.

6.3. Actuator

- The part pressed by the user's finger.
- Activates the pump system inside the spray bottle.
- Regulates the flow and atomization of the liquid into a fine spray.

6.4. Bottle (Container/Reservoir)

- Stores the liquid drug formulation (solution or suspension).
- Usually made of glass or medical-grade plastic to prevent degradation and contamination.

6.5. Dip Tube

- Extends from the actuator pump into the bottom of the bottle.
- Draws the liquid upward during actuation for continuous dosing until the bottle is empty.

6.6. Cap

- Covers the actuator and nozzle when not in use.
- Prevents contamination, dust accumulation, and accidental discharge of the spray.

Figure 3 Oral spray [25]

7. Conclusion

The present study summarizes possible formulation development and evaluation of an herbal oral spray for the effective management of sore throat, a common inflammatory condition of the oral cavity. Herbal ingredients such as Tulsi, Ginger, Mint, Clove, Aloe vera, and Honey were identified as potent natural alternatives due to their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound-healing properties. Compared to conventional synthetic drugs, herbal oral sprays provide faster absorption, higher bioavailability, and minimal side effects, making them a safe, economical, and patient-friendly approach for sore throat treatment. This study highlights the potential of herbal-based oral sprays as a sustainable and beneficial alternative to conventional therapy, supporting public health and encouraging future research in natural drug delivery systems.

Compliance with ethical standards

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References

- [1] Chris DelMar and Paul Glasziou " Sore throat" electronic publishing of journals , 2004 , (12) , 2076 – 2084.
- [2] Yash Khunt, Meet Morad, Yash Vasoya, Anish Rathod, Dishant Khakhi, Vijay Vekariya, Vishal Vora " Formulation and Characterization of a Mouth Ulcer Spray: Stability,Safety and Therapeutic Potential " International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, 2025, 6, (3) , 2582 – 7421
- [3] Rina G Maskare, Shital D Thakre, Om D Patel, Shirali S Vishwakarma, Dhyanesh N Dahake, Rima' "Novel formulation for treatment of mouth ulcer", Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Technology, 2023, 13 (1) , 19-24,
- [4] IrinA spacova , Ilke De Boeck , Eline Cauwenberghs] Lize Delanghel peter Bron , Tim Henkens , Alix Simons, imane Gangamil Leentje persoons l ingmar claes , Marianne Broek , Dominique schols , peter Delputtel Samuec loenen / veronique verhoeven I sarah Lebeer, Development of a live biotherpeutic throat spray, with lactobacilli targeting respiratory viral infections wileyonlinelibrary. com/ Journal/ mbtz2022
- [5] Crispian Scully, Stephen Porter "Oral mucosal disease recurrent aphthpous stomatitis" British journal of oral and maillofacial surgery, 2008 , 46 (3) , 198-206
- [6] M. Sri Rekha, G Sai Sri Lakshmi, N. Vijaya Lakshmi, A Tejasree, D. Srinivas Reddy "A comprehensive review on formulation and evaluation of herbal films, international journal of pharmaceutical sciences review and research, 2023, 80 (2) ,169-176
- [7] Chirag Parmar Nidhi Joshi Prachi Modi Priyamk Bhavsar Nisgta Desai and Adil Patel oral spray a review on promising drug delivery system for oral cavity Asian journal of research in medical and pharmaceutical sciences, 2022, 11 (2) , 13-21
- [8] Shulman st Bison al clinical practice guideline for the diagnosis and management of group a streptococcal pharayngitis ciln infect dis 2012 , 55 (10) , 86 -102
- [9] Worrall G. "Acute Sore Throat" can fam physician 2007, 53 (11) , 1961-1962
- [10] Stewart MG, Quality of life and health utility measures in patients with sore throat. Arch Otolaryngology Head Neck Surg. 2001 , 127 (9) , 1085-1089

- [11] Bison AL, Practice guideline for the diagnosis and management of group A streptococcal pharyngitis. *clin infect Dis.* 2002 , 35 (2) , 113-125
- [12] National Institute on Deafness and Other Communication Disorder (NIDCD). Hoarseness and sore throat.
- [13] Lopamudra Sethi, Preta Bhadra "A Review paper on Tulsi plant " *Indian Journal of Natural Science*, 2020 ,10 (60) ,20854-20860
- [14] Naila Rasheed "Ginger and its active constituents as therapeutic agents: Recent Perspectives with molecular evidence" *International journal of Health Science*, 2020 , 14 (6) , 1-3
- [15] Paul Rita and Datta K. Animesh " An update overview on peppermint" *International Research Journal*, 2211, 2 (8) , 1-10
- [16] Mayank Agrawal, Sonam Agrawal¹, Dr Radhika Rastogi , Dr Pallavi Singh, Dr Adyanthaya BR, Dr Gupta H. L "A review on uses of clove in oral and general health " *Indian Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Biotechnology*, 2014 , 2 (4)b, 1321-1324
- [17] Manpreet Singh Nanda¹, Shiv Parshad Mittal, Vipin Gupta "Role of honey as adjuvant therapy in patients with sore throat" *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology* , 2017 , 7 , (4)
- [18] Carren Teh Sui Lim, and Rajagopalan Raman "Comparison of the Efficacy Between Oral Rinse, Oral Gargel, and Oral Spray " *Journal care and Community Health*, 2012 , 3 (2) , 80-82.
- [19] Ashesr Kimchi, Garrelt Lee, M.D., Ezra Amsterdam, M.D., ken Fujii, B.S., Paul Krieg,B.S., and Dean T. Mason, M.D. "Increased Exercise Tolerance After Nitro-glycerine Oral Spray: A New and Effective Therapeutic Modality in Angina Pectoris, 1983, 67 (1), 124-125.
- [20] Rajput CG "Formulation and evaluation of natural mouth freshener spray" *International journal of pharmacognosy and clinical research*, 2020, 2 (1) , 28-31.
- [21] Mohit Hemant Sagar, Ganesh Bandu Sabane, Miss Sonawane Bharti Mitesh "Formulation and Evaluation of herbal pain relief spray" *International journal of pharmaceutical research and application*, 2023 , 8 (2) , 1712-1715.
- [22] Yuliia Maslii, Nataliia Heibina, Lina Dene, Liudas Lvanauskas "Development and Evaluation of Oro mucosal Spray Formulation Containing Plant-Derived Compounds for the Treatment of Infectious and Inflammatory Diseases of the Oral Cavity" *international journal*, 2024 , 16 (18) 2649.
- [23] Ebru Pelavan Muge Serhatli, Oznur Karaoglu, Bulent Karadeniz, Ceyda Pembeci Kodolbas, Nese Asli Oncu, Gamze Cakirca, Emel Damarli, Gunay Basdogan, Gizem Mergen Duymaz Ismail Emir Akyildiz, Gamze Duz, Sezar Acar, Yagmur Ozhan, Hande Sipahi, Mohammad Charehsaz, Ahmet Avdin. Erdern Yesilada, Cesarettin Alasalvar "Development of propolis and essential oils containing oral/throat spray formulation against SARS-CoV-2 infection" *journal of functional food*, 2022, 97, 10522.
- [24] Aakanksha m gupta dhvani j patel monalij patel Riddhi m patel Geetha m formulation and evaluation of nonei herbal throat spray containing triphala and liquorice extracts *international Delivery journal of innoratine science and research technology*, 2023,8 (5), 1461-1466.
- [25] Reem Wael Shahadha, Nichhal Khazaal Maraie "Mucoadhesive film forming spray for Buccal Drug " 2023,23(1),105-116.